

Bilding Top of Consumer's Mind Through Market Penetration: The Case of Shopee

Antoniu Kevin Tedri

managemaster.antonius.k.22@ukwms.ac.id

Master of Management Study Program –

Faculty of Business

Widya Mandala Catholic University, Surabaya

Lena Ellitan

lena@ukwms.ac.id

Faculty of Business

Widya Mandala Catholic University, Surabaya

ABSTRACT

The growth of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia has made many companies start entering the online market because people are starting to realize the benefits and convenience provided by e-commerce. The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of e-commerce, because people must quickly switch to online to meet their daily needs that are not allowed to leave the house. One of the well-known e-commerce in Indonesia is Shopee which has as of August 2021 as many as 26.92 million users according to SimilarWeb. In the e-commerce market, online businessmen are required to develop innovative marketing strategies to be able to win the competition and be able to maintain their market share. Shopee as one of the main successful players has succeeded in achieving high popularity in the eyes of consumers and Shopee has succeeded in instilling that it can become a "Top of Mind" in the minds of consumers, with its main focus on developing market penetration. This article also explains the marketing strategy implemented by Shopee, including promotions, use of social media, creative approaches, and innovative features. It also explained how Shopee was able to succeed in expanding its market share by adopting an effective marketing strategy described in the "Top of Mind" concept in the context of consumer behavior in achieving Shopee's competitive advantage.

Keywords: E-commerce, Marketing Strategy, Market Penetration, Top of Mind

INTRODUCTION

The growth of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia has become a very significant phenomenon in recent years. As a country with the largest population in ASEAN and strong economic growth, Indonesia has great potential in developing the e-commerce sector. First of all, technology adoption and increased internet access are key factors driving the growth of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia.

Received: 22 August 2023

Revised: 2 September 2023

Final Accepted 12 September 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

125

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8337936>

In recent years, internet access has become easier and more affordable across the country. In addition, the widespread adoption of smartphones in Indonesia allows people to connect to the internet and make online transactions easily. According to a report from the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers (APJII), in 2022-2023, the number of internet users in Indonesia will reach more than 210 million people (Sadya, 2023).

Support from the government and initiatives to drive the digital economy also play an important role in the growth of the e-commerce industry. The Indonesian government has launched various policies and programs to encourage the adoption of digital technology, including in the e-commerce sector. For example, the National Cashless Movement (GNNT) program aims to reduce the use of cash and encourage people to switch to non-cash transactions, including payments via e-commerce platforms. Apart from that, the digital transformation initiative launched by the government also focuses on developing infrastructure and increasing digital literacy throughout the country. The emergence of large platforms and local start-ups has also contributed to the growth of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia. E-commerce companies such as Tokopedia, Shopee, Bukalapak, and Lazada have become major players in this industry. They provide a platform that allows sellers and buyers to meet online and make transactions easily. In addition, local start-ups that focus on specific sectors, such as travel, food and fashion, have also played an important role in enriching the e-commerce ecosystem in Indonesia.

Apart from these factors, changes in people's spending behavior have also contributed to the growth of the e-commerce industry. Indonesian people are increasingly aware of the benefits and convenience offered by e-commerce, such as the convenience of shopping anytime and anywhere, various discount and promotional offers, as well as a more personalized shopping experience through customized product recommendations. The COVID-19 pandemic has also accelerated e-commerce adoption, as people have been forced to switch to online shopping to meet their daily needs. The growth of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia also has a significant economic impact. This industry creates new jobs, both in online and offline sectors, such as logistics and goods delivery. In addition, micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) also have the opportunity to market their products online and reach a wider market. This has a positive impact on economic growth and financial inclusion in Indonesia. However, challenges still exist in the development of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia. Logistics problems, such as efficient delivery and distribution of goods, are still obstacles for some e-commerce companies. In addition, consumer protection and online transaction security are also an important concern, because there are still challenges related to product authenticity, data privacy, and online fraud (Apriyani, 2020).

Marketing strategy and market penetration have a very important role in creating brand awareness and influencing consumer preferences. In today's competitive business world, building and strengthening brand awareness is the key to success for companies. Marketing strategies have a major role in creating brand

awareness in the minds of consumers. Through various marketing activities such as advertising, promotions, campaigns, and presence on social media, companies can introduce their brand to the target market. Effective marketing strategies help companies build a strong brand image and differentiate themselves from competitors. By utilizing various communication channels and relevant media, companies can reach potential consumers and attract their attention to the brand they offer. Furthermore, market penetration strategies are important in influencing consumer preferences. Market penetration focuses on expanding market share and increasing the number of consumers who use a company's products or services. By understanding consumer needs and preferences, companies can develop appropriate strategies to enter the market and reach the target audience. Market penetration strategies include a holistic approach, such as competitive pricing, targeted marketing, efficient distribution, and product innovation. In this way, companies can influence consumer preferences and ensure that their brand is the first choice in consumers' minds when they need the products or services offered.

Brand awareness and consumer preferences are intertwined. By building strong brand awareness through effective marketing strategies, companies can create high brand recognition among consumers. When consumers are familiar with a brand and have high awareness of the products or services offered, they tend to prefer that brand when they make purchasing decisions. This is due to positive perceptions formed through well-planned marketing activities. In addition, a successful market penetration strategy also plays an important role in influencing consumer preferences. By presenting products or services that are relevant and meet consumer needs, companies can build consumer trust and satisfaction. Through an effective marketing approach, companies can demonstrate the competitive advantages, uniqueness and added value of their brands. This will make consumers tend to choose the brand over competitors in the same situation. The problem formulation in this research is "How does the marketing strategy and market penetration of "Shopee" make it Top of Mind for consumers?". The purpose of this article is to analyze Shopee's marketing strategy and market penetration which makes it top of mind for consumers in the context of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia.

Literature review

Marketing strategy

Marketing strategy plays an important role in achieving a company's competitive advantage. The following are points that explain the basic concepts of marketing strategy and related components (Utami, 2021):

1. Market segmentation, namely the process of dividing the market into smaller groups based on similar characteristics, needs, or preferences. This allows companies to understand and identify market segments that are most attractive and relevant to the products or services they offer. By understanding the needs and preferences of different market segments, companies can develop more effective marketing strategies and target more precisely.

2. Targeting After conducting market segmentation, then determining the market segment that will be the company's target. Targeting involves selecting the most attractive and potentially profitable market segments for the company. This allows companies to focus on developing products, services and marketing activities that suit the needs and preferences of the target market segment. Good targeting allows companies to allocate resources more efficiently and increase the relevance of marketing messages to target consumers.

3. Positioning as a way for a company to position its brand in the minds of consumers in relation to competitors. Positioning involves efforts to create a unique and favorable perception and image for a company's brand. The purpose of Positioning is for the company's brand to be perceived as the best in terms of product excellence, added value, or meeting consumer needs. In fierce competition, effective Positioning allows companies to differentiate themselves from competitors and build emotional and rational connections with consumers.

4. Marketing mix in the marketing mix is a combination of various marketing elements used by companies to achieve their marketing goals. The marketing mix consists of four components, namely product, price, distribution (place), and promotion. Companies need to consider each of these elements holistically and execute a consistent strategy to build a strong brand image, meet consumer needs, and achieve their business goals.

Market penetration

Market penetration contributes to expanding the company's market share and achieving top of mind awareness in the minds of consumers. The following are several market penetration strategies (Mardiastuti, 2022):

1. Expanding market share, which allows companies to expand their market share by reaching new consumer segments or increasing the frequency of purchases from existing consumers. By entering new market segments, companies can take the opportunity to attract the attention of consumers who were previously unreached or unfamiliar with their brand. This can be done by identifying unmet needs and preferences of market segments, and developing appropriate products or services. On the other hand, increasing the frequency of purchases from existing consumers is also important to maximize existing market potential. With an effective penetration strategy, companies can encourage consumers to buy their products more often and maintain their loyalty.

2. Increasing top of mind awareness, namely the condition in which the company's brand or product is the first thing consumers remember when they need a relevant product or service. Through effective market penetration strategies, companies can strengthen their brand awareness in the minds of consumers. This can be achieved by increasing brand visibility through various marketing activities such as advertising, promotion, event sponsorship and presence on social media. The more frequently and strongly a brand is exposed to consumers, the more likely it is to be the first to be remembered when a need arises. By being top of mind, companies have a competitive advantage in a busy market competition and ensure that consumers choose their brands.

3. Increase competitiveness, namely companies can take advantage of economies of scale, increase competitive advantage, and strengthen their position in the market. In many cases, the greater a company's market share, the greater bargaining power it has in negotiations with suppliers or other business partners. Additionally, having a larger market share allows companies to gain more data and insight into consumer preferences, market trends, and competitors' strengths and weaknesses. This information can be used to develop more effective marketing strategies, identify new opportunities, and make more informed decisions.

4. Increasing consumer loyalty, namely providing added value, product innovation, and good customer service, companies can provide positive experiences to consumers. Through a focused penetration strategy, companies can provide products or services that meet consumer needs and wants better than competitors. Thus, consumers tend to remain loyal and choose the company's brand over competitors. Strong consumer loyalty brings many benefits, such as repeat purchases, positive referrals, and social influence that can attract new customers. With a continuous penetration strategy, companies can maintain and expand their market share and strengthen long-term relationships with consumers.

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness refers to the level of consumer awareness and knowledge of a particular brand or product. In the context of a competitive strategy, brand awareness plays a significant role in influencing consumer preferences and helping companies achieve a superior position in the market. Here are some brand awareness strategies (Hidayati, 2021):

1. Increase brand recognition i.e. Through various marketing activities such as television, radio, print and digital advertisements, companies can expand the reach of their brand and introduce it to a wider audience. Strong brand recognition provides a solid foundation in efforts to build high brand awareness. By exposing the brand consistently and repeatedly, companies can achieve a higher level of recognition in the minds of consumers, thus increasing the chances of the brand being the first choice when consumers need relevant products or services.

2. Form strong brand associations, namely building positive and strong associations between brands and the attributes or values desired by consumers. Through the right marketing messages, consistent visual branding, and satisfying customer experiences, companies can form positive and relevant perceptions in the minds of consumers. Consumers will tend to associate brands with quality, reliability, innovation, or certain values championed by the company. This helps differentiate brands from competitors and influence consumer preferences, thereby increasing brand awareness and a company's competitive advantage.

3. Encouraging word-of-mouth and recommendations with high brand awareness also plays a role in encouraging word-of-mouth marketing and recommendations from consumers. When consumers have good knowledge about a brand and have

positive experiences, they are more likely to share their experiences with others. They can recommend brands to their family, friends or colleagues based on the satisfaction they feel. In today's digital era, word-of-mouth influence can quickly spread through social media, online reviews, or community platforms. Marketing strategies that include the use of testimonials, referral programs, or collaborations with Influencers can increase brand awareness and expand brand reach through the positive influence of satisfied consumers.

4. Increase consumer loyalty, namely consumers have a high level of awareness of the brand, they tend to choose the brand as their first choice when they need a relevant product or service. Marketing strategies that prioritize customer retention, such as loyalty programs, personalized customer experiences, or superior after-sales service, can increase consumer loyalty levels. Loyal consumers tend to purchase repeatedly, provide positive references, and become brand advocates, which overall influences consumer preferences and company business growth.

Market segmentation: The Case of Shopee

Market segmentation is one of the key elements in a successful Shopee marketing strategy. In order to reach its target consumers, Shopee conducts market segmentation using a variety of comprehensive and effective approaches. First, Shopee segments based on demographic factors. Shopee considers characteristics such as age, gender, income and geographic location of consumers. By understanding the target demographic profile, Shopee can tailor product offerings, marketing campaigns and promotions that are relevant to the needs and preferences of specific consumer groups. For example, they could target marketing campaigns specifically to teenagers with products that match the latest trends, or to housewives with household products that are practical and affordable.

Apart from demographics, Shopee also considers psychographics in market segmentation. They analyze consumers' interests, lifestyles, values, brand preferences, and purchasing habits. By understanding psychological aspects and consumer behavior, Shopee can develop more personalized and relevant marketing strategies. For example, they can present product recommendations that match consumers' interests or tailor advertising content to their lifestyle. This allows Shopee to build an emotional connection with consumers and influence their preferences in choosing Shopee as their primary shopping platform.

Furthermore, Shopee performs segmentation based on geographical factors. They understand that every country or region has different cultures, customs and consumer preferences that need to be considered. By considering these factors, Shopee can adapt their marketing strategy to the uniqueness of each market. They can provide content and promotions that are relevant to local culture, present products that are popular in the area, as well as collaborate with local partners to expand the reach of the Shopee brand.

In addition, Shopee also performs segmentation based on product categories. They understand that each product category has different characteristics and target consumers. In order to maximize the effectiveness of the marketing strategy, Shopee adopts an approach that focuses on each product category. They build custom campaigns, customize promotion tactics and optimize the shopping experience for each category. For example, the marketing strategy for the fashion category will emphasize the latest trends, fashion Influencers, and interesting shopping experiences, while the marketing strategy for the electronics category will focus on superior features and competitive prices.

Positioning

Positioning is a strategy used by a company to position itself in a unique and profitable way in the eyes of consumers in a competitive market. In the context of Shopee as an e-commerce company, various effective Positioning strategies are used to highlight their unique values. Firstly, Shopee has successfully positioned itself as an innovative and user-oriented e-commerce platform. They feature an easy, safe and enjoyable shopping experience for consumers. With an intuitive and user-friendly interface, Shopee makes it easy to explore products, make transactions and interact with sellers. They also have unique features such as Shopee Live, where consumers can participate in live streaming sessions to view and buy products directly from sellers. Thus, Shopee has succeeded in creating strong differentiation and positioning itself as an e-commerce platform that prioritizes a fun and interactive user experience.

Shopee also positions itself as an e-commerce platform that provides a variety of products at competitive prices. They offer various promotional offers, discounts and vouchers that are attractive to consumers. In this case, Shopee highlights added value in terms of competitive prices and wide product accessibility. They also form partnerships with various leading brands and sellers to provide high-quality products to consumers. In this way, Shopee has succeeded in positioning itself as an e-commerce platform that provides competitive value to consumers.

In addition, Shopee also positions itself as an e-commerce platform that supports MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises). They are active in promoting local MSME products and providing opportunities for small sellers to grow through their platform. By doing this, Shopee has managed to build its image as a platform that cares about local economic development and makes a positive contribution to society. This also creates a competitive advantage for Shopee because consumers who care about social issues and want to support local MSMEs tend to choose Shopee as their shopping platform.

Promotions and Marketing Campaigns

Promotions and marketing campaigns are key elements in Shopee's competitive strategy. Through this strategy, Shopee succeeded in increasing brand awareness

and reaching the top of consumers' minds. The following are some of the promotional strategies and marketing campaigns used by Shopee:

1. Discount and Special Offer Campaigns, Shopee often launches discount campaigns and special offers such as "Shopee 9.9 Super Shopping Day" or "Shopee 11.11 Big Sale". This campaign attracts consumers' attention by offering massive discounts, shopping vouchers, and other attractive offers. The aim of this campaign is to spark consumer interest, encourage purchases, and increase sales.

2. Loyalty Programs are provided by loyalty programs such as "Shopee Coins" which allow consumers to collect points when shopping and exchange them for discounts or other prizes. This program not only encourages consumers to return to shopping at Shopee, but also builds long-term relationships with consumers because they will make repeat purchases.

3. Influencer Campaigns, namely collaborating with famous Influencers and celebrities to advertise their products and campaigns. These influencers have a large follower base and can help in increasing Shopee brand exposure. Through creative content and strategic product placement, Influencer campaigns help create brand awareness and influence consumer preferences.

4. Partnership with Famous Brands

namely partnering with well-known brands to launch special products and collaborative campaigns. For example, Shopee collaborates with leading fashion brands to launch exclusive collections that are only available on Shopee. Through partnerships like this, Shopee can enhance its brand image and offer unique products to consumers.

5. Event-Based Campaigns, namely connecting their marketing campaigns with major events such as holiday seasons, national celebrations, or other special moments. They adapt their campaigns to the theme of the event and offer relevant special discounts or promotions. This strategy helps Shopee to participate in public conversations and build emotional connections with consumers.

Product and Service Innovation

In an effort to meet consumer needs and preferences, Shopee continues to develop innovations that provide added value and differentiate itself from competitors. The following are some of the product and service innovations carried out by Shopee:

1. Live Shopping feature (Shopee Live), a feature that allows sellers to broadcast live videos explaining and showing off their products to consumers. This feature creates an interactive, real-time shopping experience, where consumers can participate in question and answer sessions, provide comments, and immediately purchase the products they see. This not only increases consumer engagement, but also allows them to get more in-depth information about the product before making a purchase.

2. 100% Authentic Guarantee Program (Shopee Mall), a platform that offers products from trusted and official brands. Shopee provides a guarantee to consumers that the products purchased at Shopee Mall are genuine and of

guaranteed quality. This provides additional confidence to consumers and increases convenience in online shopping.

3. Fast Delivery (Shopee Express), namely providing a fast and efficient delivery experience to consumers. They work closely with trusted courier services and have an extensive logistics network to optimize the delivery process. With fast delivery, Shopee can meet consumer expectations for the speed of delivery of goods.

4. The Shopee Guarantee program provides protection to consumers from fraud or products that do not match the description. This provides a sense of security and trust for consumers when making transactions on Shopee.

Shopee Market Penetration and Consumer Top of Mind

Ahead (Hafiz, 2022) wave four which was released in June 2021, Shopee ranked first in the four indicators used, namely Brand Use Most Often (BUMO), Top of mind, market share for the number of transactions, and market share for transaction value. This survey was conducted among 1,000 respondents who used e-commerce in the last 12 months, with a survey period from 26 November to 6 December 2021. In the BUMO indicator, 54% of respondents chose Shopee as the brand or platform they used most often, followed by Tokopedia (30%) and Lazada (13%). On the Top of mind indicator, Shopee also dominates with 54% of respondents mentioning Shopee as the most memorable e-commerce brand, followed by Tokopedia (27%) and Lazada (12%). In terms of market share by number of transactions, Shopee recorded the highest market share, namely 41%, followed by Tokopedia (34%) and Lazada (16%). Meanwhile, in terms of transaction value market share, Shopee also ranks first with a market share of 40%, followed by Tokopedia (30%) and Lazada (16%).

Apart from that, the Map of E-commerce in Indonesia report published by iPrice in the third quarter of 2021 also provides information regarding access to e-commerce usage in Indonesia. Tokopedia has an average of around 158.13 million website visitors per month, while Shopee is in second place with 134.38 million web visitors in the same period. However, if you look at the number of daily active visitors (Daily Active Users/DAU) of the application, Shopee has a higher number than Tokopedia. In December 2021, the Shopee application recorded 33.27 million daily active visitors, while the Tokopedia application only reached 8.82 million daily active visitors.

From these data, it can be concluded that Shopee outperformed e-commerce competition in Indonesia in the fourth quarter of 2021. Factors that influence Shopee's success include aggressive marketing strategies, excellence in brand awareness and top of mind, large market share in the number and value of transactions, and dominance in the number of daily active visitors to the application. These factors strengthen Shopee's position as one of the major players in the e-commerce industry in Indonesia.

Shopee has achieved significant success in expanding market penetration in Indonesia. There are several factors that have contributed to achieving a strong position in the e-commerce market, namely:

1. Aggressive Marketing Strategy, Shopee adopts an aggressive and innovative marketing strategy to reach consumers throughout Indonesia. By launching attractive marketing campaigns and various promotions that attract consumer attention. This marketing strategy includes using Influencers, collaborating with well-known brands, as well as advertising on various social media platforms and digital media. Through this strategy, Shopee succeeded in creating strong brand awareness and attracting consumer interest in using their platform.
2. Focus on Good User Experience, namely paying special attention to good user experience through intuitive application displays, easy-to-use interfaces and innovative features. They also offer a variety of convenient payment methods and an efficient shipping program. A strong focus on customer satisfaction has helped Shopee build long-term relationships with consumers and create brand loyalty.
3. Product and Service Innovation by continuing to innovate in products and services to meet consumer needs and preferences. Features such as Shopee Mall have been launched, which offers products from well-known brands and guarantees the authenticity of the goods, as well as Shopee Guarantee which provides protection for consumers in terms of security and reliability of transactions. These innovations help Shopee differentiate itself from competitors and provide added value to consumers.
4. Collaboration with Sellers and Brands Actively collaborate with sellers and brands to expand product ranges and improve consumer shopping experiences. They organize programs such as the Shopee Seller Awards and Shopee Mall Brands Festival which help sellers and brands to increase their visibility and expand market share. This collaboration also creates consumer confidence in the Shopee platform as a reliable shopping place.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of Shopee's marketing strategy and market penetration in the context of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia, several conclusions that can be drawn are as follows:

1. Shopee has succeeded in building strong brand awareness and becoming the brand most remembered by consumers in Indonesia. Effective marketing strategies, including creative promotional campaigns and active use of social media, have helped Shopee achieve a "top of mind" position in the minds of consumers.
2. Strong market penetration has enabled Shopee to expand its market share and achieve success in the e-commerce industry in Indonesia. Through careful use of data and analysis, Shopee is able to understand consumer needs and optimize their marketing strategies.
3. Product and service innovations carried out by Shopee have played a key role in achieving consumer preferences. By continuing to develop innovative features and improve service quality, Shopee can better meet consumer needs and differentiate itself from competitors.

4. Shopee's focus on good user experience through their app has been one of the key factors in creating consumer loyalty. By providing a user-friendly interface, easy payment process, and responsive customer support, Shopee has succeeded in building long-term relationships with consumers.

5. Seeing Shopee's success, other e-commerce industry players need to learn from the marketing and market penetration strategies that Shopee has implemented. It is important for e-commerce companies to develop effective marketing strategies, focus on user experience, and continue to innovate to remain competitive in an increasingly tight market.

Based on the aim of analyzing Shopee's marketing strategy and market penetration which makes it top of mind for consumers in the context of the e-commerce industry in Indonesia, several suggestions that can be put forward are as follows:

1. Focus on developing brand awareness, other e-commerce companies need to develop strong strategies to increase their brand awareness among consumers. This can be done through creative marketing campaigns, active use of social media, and collaboration with Influencers or celebrities who are popular in Indonesia.

2. Expand market penetration To achieve success like Shopee, other e-commerce companies need to expand their market penetration. This can be done by expanding geographic reach, increasing penetration in untapped market segments, and optimizing the use of data to understand consumer preferences.

3. Focus on product and service innovation, it is important for other e-commerce companies to continue to innovate in their products and services. Identifying unmet consumer needs and developing innovative solutions can help differentiate them from competitors and increase consumer preference.

4. Improve user experience, e-commerce companies should focus on providing a good user experience through their platforms. This includes providing a user-friendly interface, easy and secure payments, fast and reliable delivery, and responsive and personalized customer service.

5. Study trends and changes in consumer behavior, the e-commerce industry is constantly evolving and consumer behavior is also changing over time. E-commerce companies must continuously monitor these trends and changes, and actively adapt their marketing strategies to stay relevant and competitive.

References

Apriyani, T., 2020, Pengaruh E-Commerce Terhadap Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Indonesia. Diakses 17 Juni 2023 pukul 10:59 WIB., didapat dari <https://yoursay.suara.com/news/2020/02/10/162614/pengaruh-e-commerce-terhadap-pertumbuhan-ekonomiindonesia#:~:text=Pertumbuhan%20industri%20e-commerce%20tidak%20terlepas%20dari%20perilaku%20konsumen,Indon>

esia%20sudah%20mengerti%20cara%20menggunakan%20internet%20da
n%20smartphone.

Hafix, M. P. A., 2022. Shopee Vs Tokopedia, Siapa yang Menjadi Top of Mind Konsumen. Diakses 16 Juni 2023 pukul 10:55 WIB., didapat dari <https://www.marketeers.com/shopee-vs-tokopedia-siapa-yang-menjadi-top-of-mind-konsumen/>

Hidayati, K. F., 2021. 7 Langkah Tingkatan Brand Awareness agar lebih Unggul dari Kompetitor. Diakses 16 Juni 2023 pukul 08:55 WIB., didapat dari <https://glints.com/id/lowongan/cara-strategi-meningkatkan-brand-awareness/>

Mardiastuti, A., 2022. Penetrasi Pasar: Strategi, Tujuan, dan Contohnya. Diakses 16 Juni 2023 pukul 10:45 WIB., didapat dari <https://finance.detik.com/solusiukm/d-6291959/penetrasi-pasar-strategi-tujuan-dan-contohnya>

Sadya. S., 2023. APJII: Pengguna Internet Indonesia 215,63 Juta pada 2022-2023. Diakses 16 Juni 2023 pukul 11:25 WIB., didapat dari <https://dataindonesia.id/digital/detail/apjii-pengguna-internet-indonesia-21563-juta-pada-20222023>

Utami, S. N., 2021. Mengenal Segmenting, Targeting, dan Positioning (STP) dalam Pemasaran. Diakses 16 Juni 2023 pukul 12:37 WIB., didapat dari <https://www.kompas.com/skola/read/2021/11/16/100000669/mengenal-segmenting-targeting-dan-positioning-stp-dalam-pemasaran>

Yuniar, N., 2021. Shopee, E-commerce peringkat teratas di Indonesia. Diakses 18 Juni 2023 pukul 15:15 WIB., didapat dari <https://www.antaranews.com/berita/2444349/shopee-e-commerce-peringkat-teratas-di-indonesia>